

Development Schemes for Women Entrepreneur in India

R.Vennila

*Assistant Professor, PG Department of Commerce (SF)
C.P.A College, Bodinayakanur*

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Abstract

Women entrepreneur is an important phenomenon. Since there is a constant need to utilize the skill of entrepreneurship among women for economic development and women empowerment. The Government of India has undertaken several initiatives and instituted policy measures to foster a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship in the country. Job creation is a foremost challenge facing india with a significant and unique demographic advantage, india, however, has immense potential to innovate, raise entrepreneurs and create jobs for the benefit of the nation and the world. In the recent years a wide spectrum of new programmes and opportunities to nurture innovation have been created by the government of india across a number of sectors. India is soon becoming the preferred manufacturing destination of most investors' across, make in india is the Indian governemnts' efforts to harness this demand and boost the Indian economy. Make in india will affect the young entrepreneurs in a very positive way, if this programme delivers than it will bring an attitudinal change the perception of the world towards india and at the same time encourage and empower entrepreneurs to make in india.

Introduction

Women entrepreneur may be defined as a woman or group of women who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise. In terms of Schumpeterian concept of innovative entrepreneurs, women who innovate, imitate or adopt a business activity are called “Women entrepreneurs”. The emergence of women entrepreneurs and their contribution to the national number of women entrepreneurs has grown over a period of time. Several barriers and constraints, viz. cultural, educational, technological, financial and legal problems are in the way of women entrepreneurs throughout India. In some parts, women are prevented by social customs from leaving their house and going ot market. In other parts, women may be facing problems, such as lack of transport and storage facilities, market information, etc., and are also exploited by middlemen, due to poor bargaining power. It is often found that enterprises started by women and men alike mostly experience financial problems at the nascent stage of the enterprise.

Development Schemes for Women Entrepreneurs in India

Women entrepreneurs can be seen everywhere in the startup-up ecosystem of india. Women too are seen leaving their

high-profile jobs as well as some stepping out of the four walls of their homes and joining the pool of entrepreneurship in india. The major factor to jumpstart the entrepreneurial journey is capital and various banks offer specialized loans for women entrepreneurs that have slightly different and more flexible set of terms and conditions pertaining to collateral security, interest rates, etc., Here is a list of various schemes and loans exclusively for women that aim at promoting and easing out the process for them

ASPIRE

A Scheme for Promoting Innovation and Rural Entrepreneurship: This scheme is launched by government of India for promotion of Innovation, Rural Industry and Entrepreneurship on 18.03.2015. The scheme was launched mainly for promoting entrepreneurship in agro industry. Under this scheme various incubation centers set up to accelerate entrepreneurship. ASPIRE provides required skill set for establishing business enterprises. For this scheme a budget of 200cr is allotted in budget 2014.

Startup India

Through the Startup India initiative, Government of India promotes entrepreneurship by mentoring, nurturing and facilitating startups throughout their life cycle. Since its launch in January 2016, the initiative has successfully given a head start to numerous aspiring entrepreneurs. With a 360 degree approach to enable startups, the initiative provides a comprehensive four-week free online learning program, has set up research parks, incubators and startup centres across the country by creating a strong network of academia and industry bodies.

Make in India

Designed to transform india into a global design and manufacturing hub, the make in india initiative was launched in September 2014. It came as a powerful call to India's citizens and business leaders, and an invitation to potential partners and investors around the world to overhaul outdated processes and policies, and centralized information about opportunities in India's manufacturing sector.

Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP)

STEP was launched by the Government of India's Ministry of Women and Child Development to train women with no access to formal skill training facilities, especially in rural India. The programme imparts skills in several sectors such as agriculture, horticulture, food processing, handlooms, traditional crafts like embroidery, travel and tourism, hospitality, computer and IT services.

Revamped coir udyamiYojana (CUY) & Coir VikasYojana(CVY)

Coir UdyamiYojana is a credited linked subsidy scheme in coir sector that aims to integrate and develop coir units. The scheme provides 40% as Govt.subsidy,55% as Bank loan and 5% beneficiary contribution for setting up of coir units with project cost up to Rs.10 lakh. Coir VikasYojana(CVY) focuses on training for men &women coir workers also provides subsidized Ratts to women workers apart from providing assistance for setting up and expansion of coir units. This scheme also provided for participation in international and domestic exhibitions/Fairs.

Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD) Scheme

This Scheme focus on empowering women economically through trade related training, information and counseling extension activities related to trades, products, services, etc,. Financial loans are provides under this scheme by Nationalized Banks and grants by Government of india at the rate of 30% of the loan subject to maximum limit of Rs.300lakh for undertaking self-employment ventures by women in non-farm activites.

Mahila Coir Yojana

Under this scheme financial assistance is provided for motorized ats for spinning coir yarn to women artisans after giving training. Government provides motorized ats/motorized traditional ats. The remaining 25% is raised by the beneficiaries. Fund allocated for these schemes during the current year (2015-16) is Rs.6.70crore.

Atal Innovation Mission (AIM)

AIM is the Government of India's endeavor to promote a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, and it serves as a platform for promotion of world-class Innovation Hubs, Grand Challenges, start-up businesses and other self-employment activities, particularly in technology driven areas.

Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana(PMKVY)

A flagship initiative of the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) this is a Skill Certification initiative that aims to train youth in industry-relevant skills to enhance opportunities for livelihood creation and employability. Individuals with prior learning experience or skills are also assessed and certified as a Recongnition of Prior learning. Training and Assessment fees are entirely borne by the Government under this program.

Micro-credit (Rashtriya Mahila Kosh)

Established in 1993, this national level organization has been set up under Ministry of Women and Child Development.RMK provides micro-credit to women in the informal sector this credit is provided in a hassle-free manner and is offered without collateral. The organization provides loans to intermediary Organizations (IMO) which then lends to women Self Help Groups (SHGs).

Mudra Yojana Scheme for Women

This scheme is launched by the Government of India in a bid to encourage women to start their own ventures and be self-sufficient. There is no need for collateral to avail this loan.On getting verified, the concerned person will receive a Mudra card, which is like a credit card and can be used to buy required material for the business.

Conclusion

The role of Women entrepreneur in economic development is also being recognized and steps are being taken to promote women entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship must be molded properly with entrepreneurial traits and skills to meet the changes in trends, challenges global markets and also be competent enough to sustain and strive for excellence in the entrepreneurial arena.

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